

EDITORIAL

Neuroscience Research Division, CMRA, India

Introducing the official Journal of the Neuroscience Research Division of CMRA – NEURONS

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This is my pleasure to write few words for the new Journal - Neurons, where I am serving as Chief Editor. There are remarkable advancements in the field of Neurosciences during the past few years. Researches in this field has invented drugs, surgical techniques which helped in better health management; treatment in an improved way, even its impact can be seen in health policy of governments of different countries. The major objective of the journal - Neurons is to encourage Neuroscientists, Neurosurgeons, Neurologists through the Internet, especially focusing on current researches, spectrum of disease and acquire a wealth of knowledge for the benefit of the health science community by means of scientific online publication system.

In the field of Neuroscience rate of research advancements is so enormous that it takes enormous time to know properly about its application. Neurons has launched from the Neuroscience Research Division of Confederation of Medical Research Associations, Chandannagore, West Bengal, India - to bring out all the research activities from Neuroscience, Neurology, Neurosurgery, Neuropsychiatry, Neuropharmacology and all related branches under a common platform, so that advancements can be published in one journal and freely accessible worldwide for research scholars, scientists, doctors in the relevant field.

Knowledge without proper distribution has no value. Tremendous advancements of science and information technology in the last few years introduced us with World Wide Web, helping people for distribution of knowledge, the information's, advancements and achievements in all fields for the wellbeing of human civilization. We started our journal as online, so that our research team and editorial board members can provide a free of cost access of our journal from any part of this globe.

Journal editorial team will try their best to make it the most excellent quality journal by means of taking several initiatives that will improve the quality of reporting and we have given main importance to the transparency of research in general, and randomized trials in particular, by emphasizing the importance of protocols. We will consider the submissions of randomized trials only if it is registered under the recognized authority and also accompanied by a protocol, which is sent with the manuscript to the peer reviewers. We hope to make our journal one of the best journals which will always follow medical ethics, the standard criteria of scientific article publishing.

Neurons also offering a wide range of several other services which include - proof reading, peer review, setting up of the bibliography, and also English language improvement. The main maxim is to assist the authors, so that they can easily share their own research and clinical knowledge by the platform of Neurons Journal. This is our determination to make Neurons as one of the best journals in world with the effort of our research team, editorial board, peer reviewers and with everyone's whole hearted support. So we need your contribution in all of the future issues.

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At this promising moment it would be extremely remiss on my part if I don't acknowledge the contribution and express my gratitude to the many people whose blessings, active cooperation and whole hearted devotion and help make our journal to come up with a novel vision.

Regards

Dr. A.K. Pradhan

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